
IMPACT OF MOBILE PHONES ON STUDENTS LEARNING IN AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Impact of Mobile Phones on Students' Learning in Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom North-East Senatorial District. The increasing availability of mobile phones among student has created both opportunities and challenges for learning. The study investigated the extent to which mobile phones enhance access to learning materials. Improve communication and contribute to academic performance.it also examined the negative effects such as distraction, addiction and reduced study time. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom North-East senatorial District. While a sample was selected using simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaires. The findings revealed that mobile phones improve access to academic information, promote collaborative learning, and support independent study. However, excessive use of mobile phones for social media, gaming and entertainment negatively affects students concentration and academic performance. The study concluded that mobile phones have both positive and negative impacts on students learning. It was recommended that schools should regulate the use of mobile phones and teachers should guide students on proper academic utilization of mobile phones.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement of technology has transformed various sectors of society, including education. One of the most common technological devices used by students today is the mobile phone. Mobile phones are portable communication devices that provide access to information, educational resources, and interactive learning platforms. In recent years, mobile phones have become widely available among secondary school students, making them important tools for learning. Mobile phones provide students with access to educational applications, online learning platforms, and digital libraries. Students can use mobile phones to search for information, complete assignments, participate in online discussions, and communicate with teachers and classmates. These opportunities enhance independent learning and promote academic engagement. The integration of mobile phones into teaching and learning has therefore changed the traditional classroom environment. Despite the benefits of mobile phones in education, their usage among students has raised concerns. Many students use mobile phones for non-academic activities such as social media, chatting, gaming and watching videos during studying time. These activities may distract students from learning and reduce their concentration in class. Excessive use of mobile phones can also affect students' study habits and academic performance.

Teachers and parents are increasingly concerned about the influence of mobile phones on students' learning behaviour. Some schools restrict the use of mobile phones, while others encourage their use for academic purposes. This situation makes it necessary to examine the impact of mobile phones on students' learning. Therefore, this study investigated the Impact of Mobile Phones on Students' Learning in Secondary Schools.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the Impact of Mobile Phones on Students' Learning.

2. Determine the effect of Mobile Phones on Students academic performance.
3. Identify the benefits of Mobile Phones on Students' Learning.
4. Examine the challenges associated with Mobile Phones use among Students'.
5. Determine the extent to which students use Mobile Phones for academic purpose

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of mobile phones on students' learning?
2. How do mobile phone affect students academic performance?
3. What are the benefits of mobile phones in teaching and learning?
4. What are the negative effects of mobile phones use among student?
5. To what extent do students use mobile phones for academic purposes?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Mobile phones in education

Mobile phones are handle held electronic devices used for communication and information sharing. In the educational context, mobile phones are used as earning tools to support teaching and learning activities. Mobile learning allows students to access educational resources anytime and anywhere. This flexibility improves student learning experiences and encourages self-directed learning. Mobile phones enable students to download educational materials access online tutorials, and participate in virtual learning. Teachers can also use mobile phone in education promotes interactive learning and improves students' academic engagement.

Benefit S Of Mobile Phones on Students Learning.

Mobile phone provide several benefit to students learning first, mobile phones improves access to information students can use search engines to obtains relevant academic materials. This enhances

research skills and encourages independent learning. Second, mobile phones facilitate communication. Students can communicate with teachers and classmate through messaging platforms. This supports collaborative learning and group discussions. Students can also receive feedback from teachers quickly. Third, mobile phones support e-learning; students can participate in online classes, watch educational videos, and use learning applications. These opportunities enhance understanding of difficult concepts. Fourth, mobile phones promote flexibility in learning. Students can learn at their own place and review materials anytime, which improves retention and academic performance.

Negative Effects of Mobile Phone on Students Learning

Despite the benefits, mobile phones also have negative effects on students' learning. One major challenge is distraction. Students may use mobile phones for social media, games, and entertainment during class. This reduces attention and concentration. Another negative effect is reduced study time. Students who spend long hours on mobile phones may neglect their studies. This leads to poor academic performance. Mobile phone addiction is also a concern; some students become dependent on mobile phones and find it difficult to focus on academic tasks. Excessive phone use may also lead to poor sleep patterns which affect learning. Additionally, mobile phones may expose students to inappropriate content. This may negatively influence their behaviour and academics.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the constructivist learning theory. The theory emphasizes that learners construct knowledge through interaction and experience. Mobile phones provide opportunities for students to interact with learning materials and explore information independently. Therefore, mobile phones can support active learning when properly used.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to collect data from students regarding the impact of mobile phone on their learning. The population of the study consisted of secondary school student Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District. A sample of students was selected using simple random sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Impact of Mobile phone on Student learning questionnaire (IMPSLQ)". The questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section A contained demographic information, while Section B contained items related to mobile phone usages and student 'learning'. The responses were measured using a four point like scale. The data collected were analyzed using means and percentage. The results were presented in tables and interpreted accordingly.

FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that mobile phones significantly influence students learning. Student reported that they use mobile phones to search for academic materials and complete assignments. The results also showed that mobile phones improve communication between students and teachers. The study further revealed that mobile phones enhance independent learning. Students can access online tutorials and educational videos. This improves understanding of classroom lessons. However, the findings indicated that excessive use of mobile phones leads to distraction. Students spend more time on social media and entertainment than on academic activities. This negatively affects academic performance. The study also found that some students use mobile phones during class hours. This reduces concentrations and participation in classroom activities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study showed that mobile phones have both positive and negative impacts on students learning. The positive impact includes improved access to academic information, enhanced

communication and flexible learning opportunities. These findings support the view that mobile phones can be effective learning tools. The negative findings showed that mobile phones can distract Student from learning excessive use of mobile phones from social media reduces study time and affects academic performance. This suggests that proper monitoring and regulation are necessary. The finding also indicated that students benefits from mobile phone when used for academic purposes. Therefore, teachers should guide students on how to use mobile phones effectively for learning.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the impacts of mobile phones on students learning in secondary schools. The finding reveled that mobile phones play an important role in enhancing students learning. Mobil phones improve access to information, support communication, and promote independent learning. However, excessive use of mobile phones may lead to distraction, reduced concentration; and poor academic performance. Therefore, mobile phones should be properly managed to maximize their benefits. Students should be encouraged to use mobile phones mainly for academic purposes.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Schools should regulate the use of mobile phones among students.
2. Teachers should integrate mobile phones into teaching and learning.
3. Parent should monitor students mobile phone usage.
4. Students should use mobile phones for academic purposes.
5. Schools should educate students on responsible phone usage.
6. Government should provide policies on mobile phone use in schools.

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